

Steps you must follow to invest real estate and not die trying

According to [Shalom Drizin](#), a real estate investor, despite being one of the strongest and most reliable investment resources in the market, real estate can be complex to navigate for first timers

No person is born knowing how to do things. In general, an individual needs someone with more experience to guide them through the process to ensure that it is done correctly. Or, risk that all the way is much slower and more difficult, due to the narrower learning curve of the experience. The foregoing also applies to real estate investment, with the only difference that what is at stake is equity.

While real estate is safe, the [Head Officer at Fieldbridge Associates LLC](#), Shalom Drizin points out that there are many elements in the process to invest in them that can expose people. Its value can not only vary over time. In addition, there are factors such as mortgage loans, geographic location and legal requirements that must be carefully monitored. Thus, it is crucial for people to have a person who guides them step by step in the process of acquiring a real estate project.

The steps to follow to invest in real estate

The whole process will be a little different in each case, but there are some common steps that people must take into account so as not to put their assets at risk. According to Shalom Drizin, people should be very clear about what they intend to achieve with their investment in a real estate project.

In real estate there are many variants to consider. If it is a house, if it is a commercial or industrial type, or if it is land to build, as well as what better use should be given and what will be the best profitability.

Likewise, [the expert](#) Shalom Drizin points out, the expected profitability of the real estate project, both in amount and time, must be calculated. You also have to make a technical and legal diagnosis of the property, as well as determine the viability of the project once it is finished. De la Rosa says that, in any case, it will always be preferable to approach a real estate consultant to support each of these phases.